

Polarographic Behaviour of Nitroacetanilides in Presence of some Ionic and Non-ionic Surfactants *vis-a-vis* their Effect on Kinetics of the Electrode Reaction

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Polarographic behaviour of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides (in 25% ethanolic solution) has been studied at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in Britton—Robinson (BR) buffer of pH 6.1 in the presence of increasing amounts of nine different ionic and non-ionic surfactants. Each depolariser gives a single 4-electron reduction wave which has been found to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible. A decrease in the value of kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$) with the increasing concentrations of ionic and non-ionic surfactants shows that the irreversible electrode reactions of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides tend to become increasingly more irreversible. This is supported by a decrease in i_d and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ with increasing concentrations of the surfactants. A tentative mechanism of the polarographic reduction of nitroacetanilides has also been proposed at pH 6.1. The ease of reduction of the three isomers at d.m.c. is in the order, *ortho* > *meta* > *para*.

RUNNER and Wagner¹ have studied the polarographic reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides in 0.05 M LiCl and absolute ethanol buffers made of weak acids and lithium chloride and reported that the depolarisers are reduced in a single 4-electron step within the pK range 1–10. The easier polarographic reduction of nitro group in the *ortho*-isomer has been attributed to the intramolecular structure (chelation) of the compound.

This paper reports the polarographic behaviour of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides in presence of increasing amounts of ionic and non-ionic surfactants with special reference to their effect on kinetics of the electrode reaction of these depolarisers.

Experimental

o-, *m*- and *p*-Nitroacetanilides (B.D.H.) were recrystallised from ethanol before use. The other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The concentration of each depolariser (in 25% aqueous ethanol) was maintained at 1.0×10^{-3} M. A Toshniwal CLO2 manual polarograph in conjunction with a Toshniwal PL50 polyflex galvanometer was used. Purified nitrogen was used for removing the dissolved oxygen. The potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.). The number of electrons (n) involved in the reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides was determined to be 4 by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon². Having known the value of n , Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of D , the diffusion coefficient, of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides at various concentrations of the surfactants. The potential-dependent rate constant, $k_{f,h}$, was calculated by Koutecky's method^{3,4}. The kinetic para-

eters, αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$ were calculated⁵ from the plots of $\log k_{f,h}$ vs $E_{d.e.}$. Throughout the measurements, the current at the end of the drop (*i.e.* the maximum current) was recorded⁶.

The following surfactants were used, (i) cationic: lauryl pyridinium chloride (LPC), cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC) and cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), (ii) anionic: dodecylbenzene sulphate, (SLS) sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS) and Tergitol-7, and (iii) non-ionic: Triton X-100, gelatin and Decon-90.

Results and Discussion

In the absence of surfactants, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides yield sharp polarographic negative maxima at pH 6.1 of BR buffer. After the suppression of these maxima by the requisite amounts (marked by an asterisk in Table 1) of ionic and non-ionic surfactants, each depolariser gives a single well-defined 4-electron reduction wave which has been found to be diffusion-controlled. The slope values (Table 1) of log plots in each case are much larger than the theoretical value expected for a 4-electron reversible reduction process. From this it follows that the polarographic reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides is irreversible⁶. Dependence of the current on $h_{o,orr}$ at different stages of the wave^{7,8} was also studied and it was found that the current was independent of $h_{o,orr}$ at the foot of the wave whereas it was proportional to $h_{o,orr}^{1/2}$ at the plateau of the wave indicating irreversibility.

The polarographic characteristics, *viz.*, i_d , $E_{1/2}$ and D of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides have been determined in the presence of increasing concentrations of ionic and non-ionic surfactants (Table 1).

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS (α_{na} AND $k_{f,h}^0$) FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTIONS OF *o*-, *m*- AND *p*-NITROACETANILIDES

[Depolariser] = 10^{-3} M, pH = 6.1, [NaNO₂] = 0.1 M, Temp. = 25°, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.385 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$; $h_{00r} = 56.2 \text{ cm}$

[Surfactant] <i>M</i>	<i>i</i> _a μA	$\{-E_{1/2}\}$ (V) (S.C.E.)	Slope mV	<i>D</i> × 10 ⁶ cm ² s ⁻¹	α_{na}	$k_{f,h}^0$ × 10 ⁶ cm s ⁻¹
<i>o</i> -Nitroacetanilide						
LPC						
2.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ *	13.9	0.492	75	4.4		
2.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	13.6	0.500	82	4.2	0.81	2.5
CPC					0.66	2.0
2.5 × 10 ⁻⁵ *	14.2	0.494	78	4.6		
1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	13.3	0.503	91	4.0	0.69	1.9
CTAB					0.59	1.3
1.0 × 10 ⁻³ *	13.9	0.496	77	4.4		
1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	12.8	0.510	83	3.7	0.70	2.1
DBS					0.65	1.0
1.4 × 10 ⁻⁴ *	13.9	0.493	75	4.4		
6.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	13.2	0.512	88	3.9	0.72	2.8
SLS					0.62	2.2
9.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ *	14.2	0.492	76	4.6		
1.0 × 10 ⁻³	13.1	0.514	90	3.7	0.71	5.0
Tergitol-7					0.60	3.1
1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴ *	13.9	0.498	78	4.4		
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	12.8	0.513	97	3.7	0.69	3.7
Triton X-100**					0.56	1.2
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴ *	14.2	0.495	75	4.6		
1.0 × 10 ⁻³	13.9	0.512	84	4.4	0.72	3.7
Gelatin**					0.64	1.2
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	13.9	0.493	74	4.4		
1.0 × 10 ⁻³	12.3	0.522	80	3.4	0.73	5.1
Decon-90**					0.68	3.2
4.5 × 10 ⁻³ *	13.9	0.500	77	4.4		
1.0 × 10 ⁻³	11.2	0.522	91	2.8	0.70	6.6
					0.59	5.3
<i>m</i> -Nitroacetanilide						
LPC						
2.5 × 10 ⁻⁵ *	13.4	0.570	74			
1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	13.1	0.592	80	4.1	0.70	9.3
CPC					0.68	8.8
3.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ *	13.4	0.575	75			
1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	12.8	0.583	90	4.0	0.72	9.7
CTAB					0.60	7.4
2.0 × 10 ⁻³ *	13.7	0.572	75	4.3		
1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	13.1	0.597	83	3.9	0.72	10.3
DBS					0.65	7.6
1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴ *	13.4	0.570	77			
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	13.1	0.590	104	4.1	0.70	6.8
SLS					0.52	6.3
2.0 × 10 ⁻⁴ *	13.7	0.581	76	4.3		
1.0 × 10 ⁻³	12.8	0.603	93	3.7	0.71	7.8
Tergitol-7					0.58	5.4
2.0 × 10 ⁻⁴ *	13.4	0.572	75			
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	13.1	0.593	86	4.3	0.72	7.1
Triton X-100**					0.63	5.1
4.8 × 10 ⁻⁴ *	13.1	0.575	74	3.9		
1.0 × 10 ⁻³	12.8	0.588	102	3.7	0.73	8.6
					0.53	7.1

(Table Contd.)

(Table 1 Contd.)

Surfactant] <i>M</i>	i_a μA	$-E_{1/2}$ (V) (S. C. E.)	Slope mV	D $\times 10^6 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	αn_a	$k_{f,h}^0$ $\times 10^7 \text{ cm} \text{ s}^{-1}$
Gelatin**						
5.0×10^{-4} *	13.4	0.572	75	4.1	0.72	7.3
1.0×10^{-3}	11.5	0.590	83	3.0	0.65	5.5
Decon-90**						
5.2×10^{-2}	13.8	0.580	77	4.3	0.70	8.0
1.0×10^{-1}	12.8	0.595	85	3.7	0.64	5.8
<i>p</i>-Nitroacetanilide						
						$k_{f,h}^0$ $\times 10^6 \text{ cm} \text{ s}^{-1}$
LPC						
2.0×10^{-4} *	21.1	0.660	190	10.0	0.38	9.9
1.0×10^{-4}	20.5	0.665	195	9.4	0.37	9.5
CPC						
2.0×10^{-5} *	21.4	0.662	185	10.4	0.39	8.3
1.0×10^{-4}	18.9	0.680	192	8.0	0.38	5.4
CTAB						
1.1×10^{-5} *	21.4	0.662	193	10.4	0.38	7.7
1.0×10^{-4}	20.5	0.678	200	9.5	0.37	4.3
DBS						
1.3×10^{-4} *	21.1	0.660	190	10.1	0.38	8.4
3.0×10^{-4}	19.8	0.670	205	8.8	0.36	6.4
SLS						
8.0×10^{-5} *	21.4	0.665	191	10.4	0.38	8.1
3.0×10^{-4}	19.6	0.685	201	8.6	0.37	3.3
Tergitol-7						
1.2×10^{-4} *	21.1	0.663	192	10.6	0.38	7.1
4.0×10^{-4}	20.5	0.682	197	9.5	0.37	6.1
Triton X-100**						
5.5×10^{-4} *	21.1	0.660	190	10.0	0.38	7.0
1.0×10^{-3}	19.3	0.672	201	8.4	0.37	4.1
Gelatin**						
2.5×10^{-3} *	21.4	0.665	188	10.4	0.39	6.7
6.0×10^{-3}	20.2	0.682	192	9.2	0.38	6.6
Decon-90**						
4.0×10^{-2} *	20.8	0.662	191	9.8	0.38	6.3
7.0×10^{-2}	19.6	0.690	197	8.6	0.37	5.1

*Concentrations at which the maximum gets just suppressed. **Concentration expressed in percentage.

A decrease in i_a of each depolariser takes place as the concentration of the surfactants is gradually increased beyond the concentration at which the maxima get just suppressed. The $E_{1/2}$ values shift towards more negative potentials as the concentration of the surfactants is gradually increased. A decrease in i_a and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ indicate the inhibition⁹ of the electrode reactions of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides. This may be due to the coverage of the electrode surface by the molecules of the surfactants.

The reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides under the experimental conditions is analogous to the reduction of nitrobenzene. The 4-electron reduction process of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides

represents the reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides to the corresponding phenylhydroxylamine derivatives. Since the plots of $\log k_{f,h}$ vs $E_{a.e.}$ in the presence of different ionic and non-ionic surfactants are linear, there is only one rate-determining step^{10,11} involved in the reduction of each depolariser. The values of αn_a for the electrode reactions of *o*- and *m*-nitroacetanilides lie in the range 0.70–0.80, in the presence of ionic and non-ionic surfactants at their concentrations just sufficient to suppress the maxima. So, n_a , the number of electrons involved in the rate-determining step, is > 1 , because for totally irreversible systems, as in the present case, α should be less than¹² 0.5. However, only a single electron can be transferred

at a time during the course of electrode reaction⁶. A value of n_a exceeding 1 should merely mean that the successive steps are too nearly simultaneous to be distinguished on the time scale implicit in the polarographic measurements. In the case of *p*-nitroacetanilide, the value of αn_a is of the magnitude of 0.38, at the stage of just suppression of the maxima which would indicate that n_a was 1. Thus the electrode reaction of *p*-nitroacetanilide involves only one electron in the rate-determining step.

From a separate study concerning with $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots (Fig. 1) in respect of polarographic reduction of nitroacetanilides, it has been concluded that

Fig. 1. Plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH: (I) *o*-nitroacetanilide, (II) *m*-nitroacetanilide and (III) *p*-nitroacetanilide; each plot is shifted by 5 pH unit.

the number of H^+ ions involved in the rate-determining step is 1. Having thus established the stoichiometry of the rate-determining step, i.e., $n_a=2$ and $H^+=1$ for *o*- and *m*-nitroacetanilide, and $n_a=1$ and $H^+=1$ for *p*-nitroacetanilide, the following mechanism can be suggested for the polarographic reduction of nitroacetanilides at pH 6.1,

(i) For *ortho*- and *meta*-isomers :

(ii) For *para*-isomer :

αn_a and k_{γ}^0 for electrode reactions of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides decrease as the concentration of the surfactants is gradually increased from the stage at which the maxima get just suppressed. This shows⁶ that the irreversible electrode reactions of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides tend to become increasingly more irreversible with increasing concentrations of ionic and non-ionic surfactants. A decrease in i_a and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ (Table 1) with increasing concentrations of the surfactants lend support to the above conclusion. The order of k_{γ}^0 values in respect of the electrode reactions of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides, in the presence of ionic and non-ionic surfactants at the concentration at which the maxima of these depolarisers get just suppressed, is as follows : *o*-nitroacetanilide > *m*-nitroacetanilide > *p*-nitroacetanilide. Thus, *o*-nitroacetanilide is the easiest to reduce at d.m.e. followed by *m*-nitroacetanilide and *p*-nitroacetanilide.

A comparison of k_{γ}^0 values at the stage where maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroacetanilides get just suppressed by ionic and non-ionic surfactants may give a quantitative estimation of the influence of surfactants on the kinetics of the electrode reactions of these depolarisers. From a perusal of Table 1, the following order of k_{γ}^0 values in respect of various surfactants is obtained.

Electrode reaction of o-nitroacetanilide : LPC > CTAB > CPC (cationic); SLS > Tergitol-7 > DBS (anionic); gelatin > Decon-90 > Triton X-100 (non-ionic). Thus, LPC, SLS and gelatin suppress the maximum of *o*-nitroacetanilide with minimum influence on the kinetics of its electrode reaction.

Electrode reaction of m-nitroacetanilide : CTAB > CPS > LPC (cationic); SLS > Tergitol-7 > DBS (anionic); Triton X-100 > Decon-90 > Gelatin (non-ionic). Thus, CTAB, SLS and Triton X-100 suppress the maximum of *m*-nitroacetanilide with minimum influence on the kinetics of its electrode reaction.

Electrode reaction of p-nitroacetanilide : LPC > CPC > CTAB (cationic); DBS > SLS > Tergitol-7 (anionic); Triton X-100 > gelatin > Decon-90 (non-ionic). Thus, LPC, DBS and Triton X-100 suppress the maximum of *p*-nitroacetanilide with minimum influence on the kinetics of its electrode reaction.

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